

Abstract No. 11**Field Demonstrations of BWMRI Hybrid Maize 2 (Rabi) and BARI Hybrid Maize 17 (Kharif) over locations**

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Abstract On-farm demonstrations aimed to introduce, evaluate the performance and popularize newly released BWMRI Hybrid Maize 2 in Rabi season and BARI Hybrid Maize 17 in Kharif season in 502 farmers' fields across 12 districts. Seeds were sown from 8 November to 20 December 2023 (Rabi), and 22 March to 7 April 2024 (Kharif) with spacing 60 cm × 25 cm. Yield data were collected from 12 m² sample plots, converted into tons per hectare. The yield performance varied significantly across districts, with the highest yields observed in Tangail (13.73 t ha⁻¹), Panchagarh (13.63 t ha⁻¹), and Dinajpur (13.23 t ha⁻¹). In contrast, the lowest yields were reported in saline-prone districts such as Patuakhali (4.10 t ha⁻¹) and Borguna (4.50 t ha⁻¹), where a lack of fresh water for irrigation was the primary cause of reduced yields. On the other hand, BARI Hybrid Maize 17 yielded 8.05 t ha⁻¹ in Baliadangi and 7.98 t ha⁻¹ in Pirganj during Kharif season.

Keywords Maize, Rabi, Kharif, Yield**Abstract No. 12****On-Farm demonstration trials of BWMRI released wheat varieties in different AEZs of the country**

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Abstract During the Rabi 2023–24 season, a total of 286 block demonstrations were conducted in 270 farmers' fields of 23 districts under 13 AEZs of the country. Total eight wheat varieties viz. BWMRI Gom 1 (released in 2019), BWMRI Gom 2 (released in 2019), BWMRI Gom 3 (released in 2020), BWMRI Gom 4 (released in 2022), BARI Gom 25 (released in 2010), BARI Gom 30 (released in 2014), BARI Gom 32 (released in 2017), and BARI Gom 33 (released in 2017) were demonstrated in the farmer's field. The mean yield of all the eight varieties over locations was 4.01 t ha⁻¹. The highest mean yield was recorded in BWMRI Gom 3 (4.33 t ha⁻¹) followed by BARI Gom 32 (4.29 t ha⁻¹) and BWMRI Gom 4 had the lowest yield (3.52 t ha⁻¹). Considering districts, the highest mean yield was obtained from Lalmonirhat (5.03 t ha⁻¹) followed by Jhinaidah (4.87 t ha⁻¹) and Chapainawabganj (4.70 t ha⁻¹). Kurigram showed the lowest yield with an average of 3.24 t ha⁻¹ followed by Khulna (3.38 t ha⁻¹). The mean yield of wheat under farmer's conventional management was 3.3 t ha⁻¹ while the mean yield of the new eight varieties under BWMRI management was 4.01 t ha⁻¹ and the yield gap was about 18%. So, the yield gap between BWMRI and conventional management fields can remarkably be eliminated using good seeds of good varieties, seeding in optimum time and using recommended fertilizers, irrigations and other management practices.

Keywords Demonstrations, Wheat, Yield, Seeds, Management